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REACH THE NEXT LEVEL IN BLENDED EDUCATION; A HANDS-ON EXPERIENCE WITH THE EMBED FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

Blended education has worldwide risen in popularity. A lot of institutions are implementing policies and conditions in order to organise and support blended teaching as it has been shown to be an effective approach for multidisciplinary, challenge-based education. By blending online and onsite learning environments, or combining virtual and physical makerspaces and labs, a rich learning experience can be created for students. Hence, an appropriate, futureproof formal higher education context is crucial for institutions to remain or become mature in blended courses and programs.

Yet, how may academic leaders assess their status of affairs regarding blended education? How can higher education institutions bring their blended education to the next level, and make sure that it keeps improving? These questions guide the present workshop. During the workshop a framework for systematic assessment and improvement of blended education is demonstrated and employed in a hands-on experience.

Aim of the workshop

Purpose of the workshop is to raise awareness about how a formal context for blended teaching and learning may be embedded in a strategic and sustainable manner. Moreover, by using a validated framework and a set of convenient tools, the participants will assess the maturity of blended education at their higher education institution. Thereupon, they are expected to draw up an action plan. This effort will allow their institutions to (further) progress towards a higher level of maturity in blended education.

The setup of the workshop

The workshop will start with a short presentation of the European Maturity model for Blended Education (EMBED). The pillars of the maturity model, next to its dimensions and indicators are elaborated. This introduction is followed by a showcase during which the maturity of blended education at Delft University of Technology is assessed. This will be demonstrated by various existing illustrative examples.

After the introduction, the participants will assess the maturity of their own higher education institution. This hands-on experience is conceived as a collaborative

activity in different online break-out rooms. Groups of two to three participants are triggered to exchange ideas, critical reflections and practices. These group processes will be supported by prepared items for discussion and questions prompted by the workshop facilitators (two in total). Each participant is expected to draw up an action plan for their own institution.

The workshop is concluded by collecting the insights and examples of the participants in each room. These are shared with the whole group, as well as their reflections on the maturity model and a series of recommendations for its future usage.

To summarize, by the end of this workshop the participants have:

- assessed the maturity of their higher education institution, using the EMBED framework;
- exchanged ideas with other participants and get inspired by novel approaches to become more mature in blended education;
- prepared an action plan for progressing their institution towards a higher level of maturity.

Background of EMBED

The EMBED framework is a validated reference model for developing and implementing blended teaching and learning. It is conceived as a multi-actor, multilevel model and focuses therefore on different issues: the design of blended courses and programs, organizational aspects such as support and training, institutional leadership, policies and strategies in support of continuous innovation, etc. The framework is developed by a strategic partnership of six frontrunner European universities in blended education. The EMBED project was co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union. More information can be found on: <https://embed.eadtu.eu>